

IMPACT OF STACKING SEQUENCE AND THICKNESS ON COMPOSITE STRENGTH

**Toray Composite Materials America
Composite Materials Research Laboratory**

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Baltimore, USA

TORAY COMPOSITE MATERIALS US CAPABILITIES

Producer of Precursor, Carbon Fiber, and Prepreg Materials

LEGEND

- Prepreg
- Carbon Fiber Precursor
- Carbon Fiber Carbonization
- ▲ Sales Office

Toray World – Composites Division

T1100G/3960 Toughened Aerospace-Grade Prepreg

- Next-Gen 350°F (177°C) system for primary aerospace structure
- NCAMP (National Center for Advanced Materials Performance) qualified*
- Excellent balance of CAI and OHC

STORAGE LIFE

One Year (Mechanical)	180 days
One Year (Chemical)	180 days

NEAT RESIN PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

T _g (Dry)	ASTM D7028	*F (°C)	395 (202)
T _g (Wet)	ASTM D7028	*F (°C)	334 (168)
Minimum Viscosity	ASTM D4440	Poise @ *F (°C)	11.2 @ 309 (154)

RESIN VISCOSITY CURVE

LAMINA/LAMINATE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES: P173EBN-7 (T1100G UD/Gr 70)

PROPERTY	SYMBOL	METHOD	UNITS	AUTOCLAVE CURE			
				CTA	RTA	ETW ¹	ETW ²
0° Tensile Strength	F ₁₁	ASTM D3039	Ksi (MPa)	468 (3227)	476 (3282)	-	-
90° Tensile Strength	F ₃₃	ASTM D3039	Ksi (MPa)	9.70 (66.9)	10.3 (71.0)	-	-
0° Tensile Modulus	E ₁₁	ASTM D3039	Msi (GPa)	22.8 (157)	22.5 (155)	-	-
90° Tensile Modulus	E ₃₃	ASTM D2028	Msi (GPa)	1.30 (9.05)	1.20 (8.27)	-	-
0° Compressive Strength	F _{1c}	ASTM D6641	Ksi (MPa)	48.8 (336)	36.8 (254)	-	-
0° Compressive Modulus	E _{1c}	ASTM D6641	Msi (GPa)	19.5 (134)	19.4 (134)	-	-
90° Compressive Modulus	E _{3c}	ASTM D6641	Msi (GPa)	1.40 (9.65)	1.30 (8.96)	-	-
In-Plane Shear Strength @ Ult.	F ₁₂	ASTM D5379	Ksi (MPa)	18.6 (128)	13.8 (95)	-	-
In-Plane Shear Modulus	G ₁₂	ASTM D5379	Ksi (MPa)	0.80 (5.5)	0.60 (4.1)	-	-
In-Hole Compression (Barren)	OHC	ASTM D6484	Ksi (MPa)	52.1 (359)	45 (310)	41.6 (287)	37.1 (256)
Cured Ply Thickness	CPT	ASTM D3171	In. (mm)	0.0029 (0.074)			

- Long out life, extremely long freezer life

- Available in AFP tape/hand layup prepreg, unidirectional/plain-weave, FAW UD = 70/145/192 g/m²

LAMINA/LAMINATE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES: P173EBN-19 (T1100G UD/Gr 192)

PROPERTY	SYMBOL	METHOD	UNITS	AUTOCLAVE CURE				OVEN CURE				
				CTA	RTA	ETW ¹	ETW ²	CTA	RTA	ETW ¹	ETW ²	
0° Tensile Strength	F ₁₁	ASTM D3039	Ksi (MPa)	548 (3778)	546 (3778)	335 (3689)	327 (3378)	327 (3702)	-	-	-	-
0° Tensile Modulus	E ₁₁	ASTM D3039	Msi (GPa)	22.8 (173)	22.8 (172)	22.7 (170)	22.5 (167)	22.5 (169)	-	-	-	-
90° Tensile Modulus	E ₃₃	ASTM D3039	Msi (GPa)	1.46 (10.1)	1.34 (9.24)	1.13 (7.79)	0.70 (4.83)	1.31 (9.03)	-	-	-	-
0° Compressive Strength	F _{1c}	ASTM D6641	Ksi (MPa)	314 (2165)	299 (2062)	274 (1889)	200 (1379)	-	-	-	-	-
90° Compressive Strength	F _{3c}	ASTM D6641	Ksi (MPa)	50.4 (347)	37.5 (259)	23.7 (163)	16.0 (110)	-	-	-	-	-
0° Compressive Modulus	E _{1c}	ASTM D6641	Msi (GPa)	22.6 (156)	22.2 (153)	22.7 (157)	22.5 (155)	-	-	-	-	-
90° Compressive Modulus	E _{3c}	ASTM D6641	Msi (GPa)	1.58 (10.9)	1.39 (9.58)	1.27 (8.76)	1.02 (7.03)	-	-	-	-	-
In-Plane Shear Strength @ 5%	F _{12@5%}	ASTM D5379	Ksi (MPa)	19.6 (135)	15.5 (107)	9.85 (67.9)	6.42 (44.3)	-	-	-	-	-
In-Plane Shear Modulus	G ₁₂	ASTM D5379	Msi (GPa)	0.92 (6.34)	0.78 (5.38)	0.57 (3.93)	0.38 (2.62)	0.80 (5.52)	-	-	-	-
Short Beam Strength	SBS	ASTM D2344	Ksi (MPa)	22.5 (155)	18.5 (130)	10.8 (75.8)	6.85 (48.0)	17.0 (120)	-	-	-	-
In-Hole Compression (Barren)	OHC	ASTM D6484	Ksi (MPa)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Laminar Density	ρ	ASTM D792	g/cm ³	1.579								
Fiber Volume	V _f	ASTM D3171	%	57.9				56.5				
Cured Ply Thickness	CPT	ASTM D3171	In. (mm)	0.0072 (0.183)				-				

LAMINA/LAMINATE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES: P173E2N-145 (T1100G UD/Gr 145)

PROPERTY	SYMBOL	METHOD	UNITS	AUTOCLAVE CURE		
				CTA	RTA	ETW ¹
0° Tensile Strength	F ₁₁	ASTM D3039	Ksi (MPa)	552 (3807)	535 (3687)	540 (3726)
0° Tensile Modulus	E ₁₁	ASTM D3039	Msi (GPa)	23.8 (164)	23.6 (163)	24.1 (166)
0° Compressive Strength	F _{1c}	ASTM D6641	Ksi (MPa)	-	287 (1977)	-
0° Compressive Modulus	E _{1c}	ASTM D6641	Msi (GPa)	21.2 (146)	21.5 (148)	21.7 (150)
In-Plane Shear Strength @ 5%	F _{12@5%}	ASTM D5379	Ksi (MPa)	-	13.0 (90)	-
In-Plane Shear Modulus	G ₁₂	ASTM D5379	Msi (GPa)	-	0.773 (5.33)	-
In-Hole Compression (Barren)	OHC	ASTM D6484	Ksi (MPa)	-	16.8 (115.8)	-
Cured Ply Thickness	CPT	ASTM D3171	In. (mm)	55.3 (381)	48.4 (334)	42.9 (296)
Fiber Volume	V _f	ASTM D3171	%	47.8 (330)		
Cured Ply Thickness	CPT	ASTM D3171	In. (mm)	1.567		
Cured Ply Thickness	CPT	ASTM D3171	In. (mm)	0.0057 (0.145)		

- * NCAMP qualification (5-yr program from Jan. 2020)
- UD: **Complete**, NCAMP reports available upon request
- AFP slit tape: **Complete**
- PW: **On track** for completion end of 2025

Source for T1100G/3960 data sheet:

www.toraycma.com/resources/data-sheets/

Understanding the Quad Layup: Historical and Current Practice

“Quad Layup” Quasi-Isotropic, Balanced & Symmetric, $\pi/4$ increments, [25/50/25]

	1950s	1960s	1970s	1980s	1990s	Post 2000	Present Study																																																																							
Enabling Factors	"Glass Reinforced Plastic" emerged as structural materials Glass fiber Owens-Corning: 1930s -	Stiffness optimization for matching metal replacements Boron fiber Hughes Aircraft: 1960s - Carbon fiber UC, Toray: 1960s -	Failure prediction models Strength optimization (esp. notched strength)		Damage tolerance (Delamination resistance & impact tolerance) Automated manufacturing		At Toray CMA, Quad layups (OHT/OHC, UNT/UNC, ...) are either [45/90/-45/0] _n S (<i>n</i> = 1, 2, 3) or [-45/0/45/90] _n S (<i>n</i> = 1, 2, 3)																																																																							
Technical Focus	CLT developed Classical plate and shell theory to handle layered anisotropic materials	Formal adoption of CLT "Pseudo-isotropic"	Experimental validation and implementation "Quasi-isotropic"		Shift to smoother angular transition	Established with FAA certification standards Rise of AFP	Thickness effect & stacking sequence effect																																																																							
Notched Strength Consideration			AFWAL & NASA Langley on OHT/OHC [0/(±45)/90] _S , [(±60)/0] _S	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NASA Langley Workshop (1981) [45/0/-45/90]_nS OHC Boeing BSS7260 (1982) SACMA SRM 3-88 (1988) Hercules E23004DT06005 (1990) MIL-HDBK-17 (now CMH-17) on OHT/OHC testing but no specific layup	ASTM D5766 OHT (1995) ASTM D6484 OHC (1999)	ASTM D6742 FHT/FHC (2002) ASTM D8066 UNC (2017)	Focus on OHT + OHC, UNT/UNC, OTS, OCS, etc.																																																																							
Layup Studied*		Unidirectional $\pi/3$ QI (e.g., [(±60)/0] _S)	<table border="1"> <tr><td>[0/(±45)/90]_nS</td><td>9</td><td>[0/(±45)/90]_nS</td><td>14</td><td>[0/(±45)/90]_nS</td><td>8</td></tr> <tr><td>[(±45)/0/90]_nS</td><td>1</td><td>[(±45)/0/90]_nS</td><td>4</td><td>[(±45)/0/90]_nS</td><td>8</td></tr> <tr><td>[0/90/(±45)]_nS</td><td>4</td><td>[0/90/(±45)]_nS</td><td>5</td><td>[0/90/(±45)]_nS</td><td>3</td></tr> <tr><td>[90/0/(±45)]_nS</td><td>-</td><td>[90/0/(±45)]_nS</td><td>-</td><td>[90/0/(±45)]_nS</td><td>3</td></tr> <tr><td>[90/(±45)/0]_nS</td><td>1</td><td>[90/(±45)/0]_nS</td><td>2</td><td>[90/(±45)/0]_nS</td><td>3</td></tr> <tr><td>[(±45)/90/0]_nS</td><td>-</td><td>[(±45)/90/0]_nS</td><td>-</td><td>[(±45)/90/0]_nS</td><td>2</td></tr> <tr><td>[45/0/90/-45]_nS</td><td>-</td><td>[45/0/90/-45]_nS</td><td>-</td><td>[45/0/90/-45]_nS</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>[45/90/0/-45]_nS</td><td>-</td><td>[45/90/0/-45]_nS</td><td>-</td><td>[45/90/0/-45]_nS</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>[0/45/90/-45]_nS</td><td>1</td><td>[0/45/90/-45]_nS</td><td>4</td><td>[0/45/90/-45]_nS</td><td>7</td></tr> <tr><td>[90/45/0/-45]_nS</td><td>-</td><td>[90/45/0/-45]_nS</td><td>-</td><td>[90/45/0/-45]_nS</td><td>1</td></tr> <tr><td>[45/0/-45/90]_nS</td><td>1</td><td>[45/0/-45/90]_nS</td><td>3</td><td>[45/0/-45/90]_nS</td><td>9</td></tr> <tr><td>[45/90/-45/0]_nS</td><td>-</td><td>[45/90/-45/0]_nS</td><td>2</td><td>[45/90/-45/0]_nS</td><td>6</td></tr> </table>	[0/(±45)/90] _n S	9	[0/(±45)/90] _n S	14	[0/(±45)/90] _n S	8	[(±45)/0/90] _n S	1	[(±45)/0/90] _n S	4	[(±45)/0/90] _n S	8	[0/90/(±45)] _n S	4	[0/90/(±45)] _n S	5	[0/90/(±45)] _n S	3	[90/0/(±45)] _n S	-	[90/0/(±45)] _n S	-	[90/0/(±45)] _n S	3	[90/(±45)/0] _n S	1	[90/(±45)/0] _n S	2	[90/(±45)/0] _n S	3	[(±45)/90/0] _n S	-	[(±45)/90/0] _n S	-	[(±45)/90/0] _n S	2	[45/0/90/-45] _n S	-	[45/0/90/-45] _n S	-	[45/0/90/-45] _n S	1	[45/90/0/-45] _n S	-	[45/90/0/-45] _n S	-	[45/90/0/-45] _n S	1	[0/45/90/-45] _n S	1	[0/45/90/-45] _n S	4	[0/45/90/-45] _n S	7	[90/45/0/-45] _n S	-	[90/45/0/-45] _n S	-	[90/45/0/-45] _n S	1	[45/0/-45/90] _n S	1	[45/0/-45/90] _n S	3	[45/0/-45/90] _n S	9	[45/90/-45/0] _n S	-	[45/90/-45/0] _n S	2	[45/90/-45/0] _n S	6			Comparison of quad layups with different ply orderings and counts [-45/0/45/90] _n S vs. [-45/90/45/0] _n S Effect of θ Broader stacking sequence effects
[0/(±45)/90] _n S	9	[0/(±45)/90] _n S	14	[0/(±45)/90] _n S	8																																																																									
[(±45)/0/90] _n S	1	[(±45)/0/90] _n S	4	[(±45)/0/90] _n S	8																																																																									
[0/90/(±45)] _n S	4	[0/90/(±45)] _n S	5	[0/90/(±45)] _n S	3																																																																									
[90/0/(±45)] _n S	-	[90/0/(±45)] _n S	-	[90/0/(±45)] _n S	3																																																																									
[90/(±45)/0] _n S	1	[90/(±45)/0] _n S	2	[90/(±45)/0] _n S	3																																																																									
[(±45)/90/0] _n S	-	[(±45)/90/0] _n S	-	[(±45)/90/0] _n S	2																																																																									
[45/0/90/-45] _n S	-	[45/0/90/-45] _n S	-	[45/0/90/-45] _n S	1																																																																									
[45/90/0/-45] _n S	-	[45/90/0/-45] _n S	-	[45/90/0/-45] _n S	1																																																																									
[0/45/90/-45] _n S	1	[0/45/90/-45] _n S	4	[0/45/90/-45] _n S	7																																																																									
[90/45/0/-45] _n S	-	[90/45/0/-45] _n S	-	[90/45/0/-45] _n S	1																																																																									
[45/0/-45/90] _n S	1	[45/0/-45/90] _n S	3	[45/0/-45/90] _n S	9																																																																									
[45/90/-45/0] _n S	-	[45/90/-45/0] _n S	2	[45/90/-45/0] _n S	6																																																																									

*ASTM-recommended QI (D5766, D6484, ...)

“Typically a [45_i/-45_i/0_j/90_k]_nS tape should be selected such that a minimum of 5 % of the fibers lay in each of the four principal orientations”

Industry Adoption of Quad Layup: Observations across Test Campaigns

Midplane Ply	Layup	Ply Count	Material	UNT	OHT	FHT	UNC	OHC	FHC
0°	[45/90/-45/0]S	8	UD2	-	Customer A	Customer A	-	-	-
	[45/90/-45/0]2S	16	UD1						
			UD1						
			UD4						
			UD2	-	Customer D	-	-	Customer D	-
			UD2	-	-	-	-	Customer A	-
	[45/90/-45/0]3S	24	UD1						
			UD4						
			UD2	-	-	-	-	Customer D	-
90°	[45/0/-45/90]S	8	UD2	-	Customer E	-	-	Customer E	-
	[45/0/-45/90]2S	16	UD1						
			UD1						
			UD1						
			UD2	Customer G	Customer G	Customer G	Customer G	-	-
	[45/0/-45/90]3S	24	UD1						
			UD2	-	-	-	-	Customer G	Customer G

*FAW = 190 g/m² for all materials above

Project Goals and Motivation

- Understand how stacking sequence and thickness influence mechanical performance
 - Aim at demystifying variability across reported data
 - Support customer design decisions by clarifying expected performance ranges
 - Recommend optimized test layups in order to broaden and secure design space

Phase 1.

- Review historical data to identify *Thickness Effect* and *Stacking Sequence Effect* from Toray's material DB
- Test 0° Tension and Quad OHT/OHC, T1100G/3960, FAW = 190 g/m² (CPT = 7.2 mil, 0.18 mm)
*Fiber Areal Weight *Cured Ply Thickness

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Phase 2.

- Test UD/Quad Compression, Quad UNT/UNC, T1100G/3960, FAW = 190 g/m²
- Test 0° Tension, Quad OHT, CLC, T1100G/3960, FAW = 70 g/m² (CPT = 3 mil, 0.076 mm)
- Expand test matrix to varied thicknesses by ply count control

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TBD

Phase 3.

- Test Quad OHT with varied stacking sequences, T1100G/3960, FAW = 190 g/m²
- Test Quad OHT hybridized with other materials, T1100G/3960, FAW = 190 g/m²
- Test Soft/Hard OHT with varied stacking sequences, T1100G/3960, FAW = 190 g/m²

TBD

TBD

TBD

Test Matrix Overview: Phases 1 & 2

Tension	Test Method	Layup	Test Condition		Compression	Test Method	Layup	Test Condition
TS UD	ASTM D3039 0.5" x 10" (15 x 250 mm)	[0]2	RTA CTA -75°F ETW 180°F	Phase 1	CLC UD	ASTM D6641 0.5" x 5.5" (12 x 140 mm)	[0]4	RTA
		[0]4					[0]6 (NCAMP)	
TS Quad	ASTM D3039 0.5" x 10" (15 x 250 mm)	[0]8	RTA	Phase 2	CLC Quad	ASTM D6641 0.5" x 5.5" (12 x 140 mm)	[0]16	RTA
		[0]12					[0]16	
UNT	ASTM D5766 1.5" x 12" (38 x 300 mm)	[45/90/-45/0]S	RTA	Phase 2	UNC	ASTM D8066 1.5" x 12" (38 x 300 mm)	[45/90/-45/0]S	RTA
		[45/90/-45/0]2S					[45/90/-45/0]3S	
OHT	ASTM D5766 1.5" x 12" (38 x 300 mm)	[45/90/-45/0]3S	RTA CTA -75°F	Phase 1	OHC	ASTM D6484 1.5" x 12" (38 x 300 mm)	[45/90/-45/0]3S	RTA ETW 180°F
		[45/90/-45/0]4S					[45/90/-45/0]4S	
		[-45/0/45/90]S	RTA CTA -75°F	Phase 1			[-45/0/45/90]S	RTA ETW 180°F
		[-45/0/45/90]2S (NCAMP)			[-45/0/45/90]2S (NCAMP)	[-45/0/45/90]3S (NCAMP)		
		[-45/0/45/90]3S					[-45/0/45/90]3S	
		[-45/0/45/90]4S					[-45/0/45/90]4S	

Planned due to UNT Limitations

Phase 1 Results: UD Tension, RTA CTA & ETW

Phase 1.

- Test 0° Tension and QI OHT/OHC, T1100G/3960, FAW = 190 g/m² (CPT = 7.2 mil, 0.18 mm)

Phase 1 Results: Quad Notched Strengths

Phase 1.

- Test 0° Tension and QI OHT/OHC, T1100G/3960, FAW = 190 g/m² (CPT = 7.2 mil, 0.18 mm)

Quad Layups

[45/90/-45/0]S [45/90/-45/0]2S [45/90/-45/0]3S [45/90/-45/0]4S [-45/0/45/90]S [-45/0/45/90]2S [-45/0/45/90]3S [-45/0/45/90]4S

Notes:

- OHC Coupon Strain measured 0.85 mm from hole edge Grid size = 1.2 x 0.6 mm
- OHT Strain computed from test frame's displacement

Phase 2 Results: UD and Quad Compression

CLC 0° UD- RTA

CLC Quad Layups-RTA

Compressive Strength UD Layups

- [0]4 [0]6
- [0]8 [0]14
- [0]16 [0]20

UNC Quad Layups-RTA

UNT Quad Layups-RTA

Compressive Strength Quad Layups

- [45/90/-45/0]S [-45/0/45/90]S
- [45/90/-45/0]2S [-45/0/45/90]2S
- [45/90/-45/0]3S [-45/0/45/90]3S
- [45/90/-45/0]4S [-45/0/45/90]4S

Phases 1 & 2: Strength vs. Ply Count For Quad Layups

Test (Method)	Width & Length	Gage Section
UNT (ASTM D8066)	1.5" x 12" (38 x 305 mm)	8" (203 mm)
OHT (ASTM D8066)	1.5" x 12" (38 x 305 mm)	8" (203 mm)
UNC (ASTM D8066)	1.5" x 12" (38 x 305 mm)	4" (100mm)
OHC (ASTM D6486)	1.5" x 12" (38 x 305 mm)	4" (100mm)
CLC (ASTM D6641)	0.5" x 5.5" (12.7 x 140 mm)	0.5" (12.7 mm)

Phases 1 & 2: Strength vs. Ply Count- UD Tests

Test (Method)	Width & Length	Gage Section
0° TS (ASTM D8066)	1.5" x 12" (38 x 305 mm)	8" (203 mm)
CLC (ASTM D6641)	0.5" x 5.5" (12.7 x 140 mm)	0.5" (12.7 mm)

0° Tensile Strength-UD

0° CLC Strength-UD

Compressive Strengths Summary & Comparison

CLC 0° UD RTA	CLC RTA Quad-0°	CLC RTA Quad-90°	UNC RTA Quad-0°	UNC RTA Quad-90°	OHC RTA Quad-0°	OHC RTA Quad-90°	OHC ETW Quad-0°	OHC ETW Quad-90°

Compressive Strengths vs. Ply Count

Normalized Compressive Strengths vs. Aspect Ratio

Tensile Strengths Summary & Comparison

0° UD RTA	0° UD CTA	0° UD ETW	UNT RTA Quad-0°	UNT RTA Quad-90°	OHT RTA Quad-0°	OHT RTA Quad-90°	OHT CTA Quad-0°	OHT CTA Quad-90°

Tensile Strengths vs. Ply Count

Normalized Tensile Strengths vs. Aspect Ratio

Unidirectional Thickness effects

- Tensile strength (including 0°TS, OHT, UNT) tends to decrease with increasing thickness
- Compressive strength (including 0°CS, OHC, UNC) tends to increase with increasing thickness

UNT/UNC, OHT/OHC Quad Layup Thickness Effects

- High scatter at ply count = 8, becomes more consistent as ply count increases
- Outliers in thin layups deserve further replication
 - Observed ~10% increase for 8-ply OHT depending on center orientation

Summary and Design Implications-Quad Layup Choices

Stacking sequence effect in quad layup

- Quad layups with 0° in the midplane performs better, especially in tension
- Differences diminish as ply count increases
- Strength variability higher at low ply counts – stabilizes with thickness

Design implications

- Thin layups should avoid relying solely on 0° strength, thicker laminates show more reliable compression performance
- A shared *thick* panel for OHT/OHC, UNT/UNC, FHT/FHC streamlines layup, reduces lab workload, and minimizes potential confusion in lab workflows

- Quad layup stacking sequence significantly influences strength, particularly in thin laminates
- 0° plies in the midplane enhance tensile and compressive strength, with larger effects at low ply counts
- Thickness impacts both performance and variability – strength stabilizes with increased thickness
- High OHT outliers are repeatable and valid, warranting further targeted testing
- Future work: Expand test matrix with varied FAW and hybridized systems

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